

A STUDY ON CONSUMER AWARENESS, ATTITUDE AND PREFERENCE TOWARDS HERBAL COSMETIC PRODUCTS (With Special Reference to Udumalpet Taluk)

M. Vasuhi* & R. Kavitha Rani**

* Head, Department of B.Com (CA), Vidyasagar College of Arts and Science, Udumalpet, Tamilnadu

** M.Phil Research Scholar, Vidyasagar College of Arts and Science, Udumalpet, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: M. Vasuhi & R. Kavitha Rani, "A Study on Consumer Awareness, Attitude and Preference towards Herbal Cosmetic Products (With Special Reference to Udumalpet Taluk)", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 1, Issue 1, Page Number 64-66, 2016.

Abstract:

Cosmetics and toiletries are not just the domain of women more body sprays, perfumes and other cosmetics and toiletries with rising demand from men, the Indian market is getting enlarged and many players are coming out with cosmetic products especially skin care products for women and men Globalization will certainly increase cosmetic products penetration and all professional shall equip themselves to exploit opportunities offered by this sector. This gives me an opportunity to work on with endeavor focusing on the consumer perception and satisfaction of women towards cosmetics with special reference to Herbal Products.

Key Words: Herbal, Cosmetics & Attitude

1. Introduction:

The concept of beauty and cosmetics is an ancient as mankind and civilization women are obsessed with looking beautiful. So they use various beauty products that have herbs to look charm and young. Indian herbs and its significance are popular worldwide. Herbal cosmetics have growing demand in the nature. There are a wide range of women around the world. The Indian cosmetics industry has a plethora of herbal cosmetics brands like Himalaya Herbal, Lotus Herbal, Khadi Herbal, and many more adding to the list. The Indian cosmetics market is defined as skin care, hair care, color cosmetics, fragrances and oral care segments.

Statement of the Problem:

Consumers are the masters of their money and they have an enormous influence on the economic market change because they possess the ability to implement and coordinate their choice of spending or saving in the purchase decision. Consumers are influenced by their attitude towards the product and therefore marketers need to implement their strategies and tactics frequently in order to achieve more consumers. Satisfaction and accurate target in finding out what customers are aware off and their attitude and there by offering products according to this needs will help the industry stake holders to enrich their customer experience and accelerate growth of the market.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the consumer awareness of herbal cosmetic products.
- ✓ To study about the factor influencing the consumer to use the herbal cosmetic products.

Scope of the Study:

The present study will be helpful in understanding the consumer attitude of the different strata people in the Indian society especially in Udumalpet Taluk, Tamil Nadu towards Herbal Cosmetic Products. The classification of the different strata of the people in area wise, gender wise, age wise, income wise, etc.... The study will also be helpful in analyzing the customer attitude towards the different factors identified after the focus group discussions for the future studies by the researchers and academicians.

Methodology:

The methodology adopted for the present study consists of six parts they are

Period of the Study:

The study was conducted for a period of six months

Sources of Data:

The study is based on primary data collection. The data has been collected from the users of herbal cosmetics products. The secondary data was collected from the articles, journals, newspapers and various websites; it has been used in the review of literature, chapter and Profile of the organizations.

Sampling Design of the Study:

The sampling technique in this project is convenient sampling. The sample size comprises of different types of users who are using herbal cosmetic products. A sample of 50 respondents was taken into account for finding their uses for the herbal cosmetic products.

Tools for Analysis:

The following are the tools applied on the respondents given by the respondents to analyze and derive the result.

- ✓ Karl Pearson's co-efficient of correlation

- ✓ Average Ranking analysis

Limitation of the Study:

- ✓ The area was wide since it is confined only to Udumalpet Taluk so results cannot be universally accepted.
- ✓ The study is limited to the sample size of 50 respondents only. So this cannot be a “full proof”.

2. Review of Literature:

Mitra & Kapoor (2009) state tannins are important complex organic compounds; such are partially covered in vegetable color yielding materials. These are important agro-chemical. Which create affinity between adjective dyes and hairs? The main source of tannins is the bark and wood of acacia, oak, wattle, etc.

According to the study conducted by Dr. Vinith Kumar Nair and Dr. Prakash Pillai R (2010) male consumers generally prefer to purchase and make the brand selection of cosmetics individually. Quality is the major factor influencing the purchase decision of male consumers.³

According to the study conducted by Ashok Yakkaldevi(2013) on the consumer behavior towards cosmetics apart from psychology and economics the role of history and tradition in shaping the Indian consumer behavior is quite unique. Consumers are also associated with values of care and affection.

3. Profile of Herbal Cosmetics Brands:

Himalaya Herbals:

Himalaya Herbals is a range of 100% natural and safe products with rare herbs collected from the foothills of the Himalayas. Each product combines the best of Ayurveda with years of dedicated research.

Lotus Herbals:

Lotus Herbals is India’s leading natural cosmetics company. Combining ancient wisdom from the Vedas with 21st century technology, it’s range of over 250skincare, hair care, sun care and make-up products for the retail and Professional markets.

Vaadi Herbals:

Vaadi herbals Pvt Ltd has combined Ayurvedic science with modern technology to develop a whole new range of personal care products. Its range consists of hair care, skin care, and face care and body care products enriched with the extracts of best quality natural herbs to cater to the needs of the whole family.

Just Herbs:

Just Herbs is a company which is the embodiment of the old or traditional and the new or modern. The Aurvedic Bhaishajyas (texts) makes it old and new because it brings forward the modern ready-to-use forms.

4. Analysis and Interpretation:

A) Karl Pearson’s Co-Efficient of Correlation:

Table - 1

Let monthly family income per month of the respondents taken as (X) and spending for herbal cosmetics product per month of the respondents taken as (Y).

Coefficient of Correlation:

Income and Spending Level on Herbal Cosmetic Products per Month:

Income	Spend	X=x-x	Y=y-y	X ²	Y ²	XY
17	21	4.5	8.5	20.25	72.25	38.25
14	17	1.5	4.5	2.25	20.25	6.75
10	7	-2.5	-5.5	6.25	30.25	13.75
9	5	-3.5	-7.5	12.25	56.25	26.25
50	50	0	0	41	179	85

The correlation value between family income per month and spending for herbal cosmetics product per month is 1. So there exist of perfect positive correlation between the two factors.

B) Average Ranking Analysis:

Average ranking analysis is used to analyses the ranks given by the respondents for various factors, the weights has given to various ranks and total scores are calculated based in total scores and then the ranks are allotted according to average ranking scores.

Table - 2

Average Ranking Analysis:

Ranking Factor Influencing By the Respondents:

Factor	6	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Rank
Price	3	10	10	9	8	5	50		
Score	48	50	40	27	16	5	186	3.72	4
Quality	13	11	10	8	4	4	50		
Score	78	55	40	24	8	4	209	4.18	1
Quantity	12	12	9	8	6	3	50		
Score	72	60	36	24	12	3	207	4.14	2
Packing	6	8	9	11	9	7	50		

Score	36	40	36	33	18	7	170	3.4	5
Flavor	7	5	7	8	11	12	50		
Score	42	25	63	24	22	12	188	3.76	3
Offer	4	4	5	6	12	19	50		
Score	24	20	20	18	24	19	125	2.5	6

The above table reveals that the respondents have assigned “Quality” was the primary factor (Rank I) and “Price” as the next factor (Rank II), third rank to flavor, fourth rank to quantity, fifth rank to packing, and sixth rank to offer.

5. Findings Suggestion sand Conclusion:

Findings:

- ✓ There exist of perfect positive correlation between the two factors. I.e. family income per month of the respondents and spend for herbal cosmetics product per month of the respondents.
- ✓ Majority of respondents, ranked first to quality of the product.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between age and period of using the products.
- ✓ There no relationship between Educational Qualification and level of satisfaction about herbal cosmetics products.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The price of the herbal cosmetics product can be reduced which would attract more customers.
- ✓ The manufacturers could reduce the chemical combination in the herbal cosmetics products.
- ✓ The manufacturers can conduct a survey for knowing the consumer need.
- ✓ Window display is also an attractive method for attracting the minds of the people, especially the housewives.

Conclusion:

The study reveals that most of the respondents are aware of the herbal cosmetics. The people now are not considering the cosmetics as luxury, most of the consumers feel that there are more chemicals in cosmetics, which cause many side effects, and started switching over to herbal based cosmetics. The cosmetic manufacturing company after realizing the need of the customer started providing herbal based cosmetics. Many respondents feel that there is more chemical combinations in the herbal cosmetics, which can be reduce by the manufactures, so that t would increase its usage by the customers. This study enables the manufactures to know the need and preference of the customers which can be implemented by them to improve their products.

References:

1. Mitra R and Kapoor V P (1999), Tannins containing plants part II: Historey, distribution, sources and uses. In: Appied Botany Abstract, NBRI, Lucknow, and Vol. 19(4), pp. 279-314.
2. Dr. Vinith Kumar Nair and Dr. Prakash Pillai R, International Marketing Conference on “Marketing & Society”, 8-10 April, 2007, IIMK.
3. Fan Shean Cheng, Cheng Soon Ooi, and Ding Hooi Ting, International Review of Business Research Papers, Vol.6 (1) February 2010, Pp. 574-590.
4. Sundari, R & Murugan, MS 2011, „Brand Loyalty”s Influence on Women”s Buying Behavior with Special Reference to Personal Care Products”, International Journal of Commerce, IT and Management”. Vol. 1(2), pp. 56-62.
5. K. Veerakumar (2016) article titled “A Study on Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Brand Loyalty” International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-I, June – 2016. P.No.661-663.
6. R. P. Manjula & Dr. R. Shanmugan (2016) “A Study on Customer Preference towards Cyber Crime with Banking Industry” International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Vol-II, Issue-I, 2016. P.No.597-603.
7. T. M. Shankar (2016) “An Empirical Study on Customer Awareness, Preference and Satisfaction on Private Label with Special reference To ‘Reliance Select’ in Coimbatore City” International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-I, 2016.P.No.494-503.
8. V. Sini & Dr. C. R. Karpagam (2016) “A Study on Policy Holders Awareness and Preference towards Health Insurance” International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-II, 2016.P.No.23-28.
9. <http://www.Makingcosmetics.com/index.htm>
10. <http://www.theherbarie.com/index.html>
11. <http://www.bluvenus.com/SW/herbal/index/htm>